

NAJ FNR

THE NORTH AFRICAN JOURNAL OF
FOOD AND NUTRITION RESEARCH

Making Nutrition a Development Priority in Africa

The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research

<https://www.najfnr.org>

najfnr@najfnr.org

The NAJFNR

Editorial Board Members

September 2020

eISSN: 2588-1582

NAJFNR-2588-1582

Editor's Quote

"The Mediterranean diet, known to maintain good health and promote longevity, has been gradually abandoned by populations in Southern Europe, North Africa, and the Near East as reported by the F.A.O. High rates of overweight and obesity, as reported by several studies, are not limited to the European Mediterranean countries (Greece, Italy, Spain, Portugal) and recalls what the W.H.O. says for two years: emerging economies are increasingly affected.

During the last few decades, there has been a great interest in the field of nutrition and health. *The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research* aims to encourage scientists and physicians of all fields to publish their works in order to promote nutrition and education among all concerned communities in North Africa. Furthermore, the purpose of the journal is to provide balanced, reliable, and updated data for researchers and health care professionals to facilitate decisions and management of metabolic diseases related to nutritional status."

Prof. Meghit Boumediene KHALED
Editor-in-Chief /Founder

Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes
Faculty of Life and Natural Sciences
Department of Biology
Human Nutrition, Biochemistry and Food Science (HNBFS)-Team Leader
ALGERIA.
<https://www.najfnr.org>
Tel. +213 551152261

Editor-in-Chief

Pr. Meghit Boumediene KHALED Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA khaled@khaledmb.co.uk

Managing Editor

Dr. Mustapha DIAF Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA diafmustapha@gmail.com

Advisory Editors

Pr. Hassan AGUENAOU	Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, MOROCCO	aguenao2014@gmail.com
Pr. Rachid MALEK	University Hospital of Sétif, Internal Medicine, ALGERIA	rmalekdz@gmail.com
Pr. Amos LAAR	University of Ghana, GHANA	amos.laar@gmail.com
Pr. Basil H. ABOUL-ENEIN	Faculty of Public Health & Policy, London, UK.	Basil.Aboul-Enein@lshtm.ac.uk
Dr. Nada BENAJIBA	Princess Nora bint Abdul Rahman University, Riyadh, KSA	benajibanada@gmail.com
Dr. Ferzana SALEH	University of Health Sciences Dhaka, BANGLADESH	salehfarzana42@gmail.com
Dr. Farid DAHMOUNE	Mohand Oulhadj University of Bouira, ALGERIA	farid.dahmoune@yahoo.fr
Dr. Bachir BENARBA	Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara, ALGERIA	bachirsb@yahoo.fr
Dr. Mohammed GAGAOUA	INRA - UMRH. C.R Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, FRANCE	Mohammed.GAGAOUA@inra.fr
Dr. Poorna Chandra Rao YALAGALA	Department of Medicine, University of Illinois, Chicago, USA	yalagala@uic.edu
Dr. Kaddour ZIANI	Tahar Moulay University of Saïda, ALGERIA	zianivet07@gmail.com
Dr. Hamid El BILALI	Univ. of Natural Resources and Life Sci. Vienna, AUSTRIA	elbilali@boku.ac.at
Dr. Slimane MEHDAD	Mohammed V University, Rabat, MOROCCO	slimanemehdad@gmail.com
Dr. Moez Al Islam Ezzat FARIS	College of Health Sciences, University of Sharjah, UAE	mfaris@sharjah.ac.ae

Specialty Editors

Pr. Hassan AGUENAOU	Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, MOROCCO	aguenao2014@gmail.com
Pr. Miloud SLIMANI	Taher Moulay University of Saida, ALGERIA	miloud.slimani@univ-saida.dz
Pr. Leila HOUTI	Ahmed Ben Bella University of Oran 1, ALGERIA	leilahouti@yahoo.fr
Pr. Kaddour BOUDEROUA	Abdelhamid Ibn Badis Univ. of Mostaganem, ALGERIA	bouderouak@gmail.com
Pr. Chafia TOUIL-BOUKOFFA	Univ. of Sci. and Tech. Houari Boumediene, ALGERIA	touilboukoffa@yahoo.fr
Pr. Jaafar HEIKEL	University Mohammed 6 Polytechnic, MOROCCO	drjheikel@gmail.com
Pr. Rachida ALLEM	Hassiba Benbouali University of Chlef, ALGERIA	rachidalem2001@yahoo.fr
Pr. Khodir MADANI	Abderrahmane Mira University of Bejaia, ALGERIA	madani28dz2002@yahoo.fr
Pr. Rehia BELAHSEN	Chouaïb Doukkali University of El Jadida, MOROCCO	b.rehia@gmail.com
Pr. Henrietta ENE-OBONG	University of Calabar, Depart of Biochemistry, NIGERIA	nkeneobong@yahoo.com
Pr. Khedidja MEKKI	Ahmed Ben Bella University of Oran 1, ALGERIA	khmekki@hotmail.com
Dr. Mustapha DIAF	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	diafmustapha@gmail.com
Dr. Mohamad Ghassan ABIAD	American University of Beirut, LEBANON	ma192@aub.edu.lb
Pr. Zoubida ZAIDI	Univ. Hosp, Ferhat Abbas University of Setif, ALGERIA	zozaidi@yahoo.fr
Pr. Malika BENDAHMANE	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	maliabendaman@gmail.com
Pr. Amos LAAR	University of Ghana, GHANA	amos.laar@gmail.com

Associate and Review Editors

Pr. Abdelmalek BOUZID	University of Constantine 3, Constantine, ALGERIA	bouzid.abdelmalek@yahoo.fr
Pr. Rachid MALEK	University Hospital of Sétif, Internal Medicine, ALGERIA	rmalekdz@gmail.com
Pr. Reema Fayez TAYYEM	University of JORDAN, Amman, Al-Jubeiha, JORDAN	r.tayyem@ju.edu.jo
Pr. Abdelmajid SOULAYMANI	Ibn Tofail University, Kenitra, MOROCCO	soulaymani@uit.ac.ma
Pr. Basil H. ABOUL-ENEIN	Faculty of Public Health & Policy, London, UK.	Basil.Aboul-Enein@lshstm.ac.uk
Pr. Jamal BELKHADIR	France Avenue, Agdal, Rabat, MOROCCO	jamalbelkhadir@yahoo.fr
Pr. Fatima-Zahra AZZAOU	Hassan II University, Casablanca, MOROCCO	azzaouifz@hotmail.com
Pr. Jalila EL ATI	National Institute of Nutrition and Food Technology, TUNISIA	jalila.elati@yahoo.fr
Pr. Khaled KAHLOULA	Tahar Moulay University of Saida, ALGERIA	kahloulakhaled@yahoo.fr
Pr. Amina BARKAT	Nat. Cent. of Neonatology and Nutrition, Rabat, MOROCCO	barakatamina@hotmail.fr
Pr. Rachida ROKY	Hassan II University, Casablanca, MOROCCO	rokyrachida@gmail.com
Pr. Malika BARKAT	INATAA, Constantine, ALGERIA	barkat.inataa@yahoo.fr
Pr. Ahmed BOUALGA	Ahmed Ben Bella University of Oran 1, ALGERIA	boualga.ahmed@gmail.com
Pr. Lotfi MOUNI	Akli Mohand Ouelhadj University of Bouira, ALGERIA	lotfimouni@gmail.com
Pr. Souad BENAICH	Faculty of Sciences, Rabat, MOROCCO	souadbenaich@gmail.com
Pr. Hayet OULAMARA	University Mentouri of constantine, ALGERIA	houlamara@yahoo.fr
Pr. Francis ZOTOR	Univ. of Health and Allied Sciences, Ho, Volta Region, GHANA	francisfirst@gmail.com
Dr. Nada BENAJIBA	Princess Nora bint Abdul Rahman University, Riyadh, KSA	benajibanada@gmail.com
Pr. Slimane MEHDAD	Mohammed V University, Rabat, MOROCCO	slimanemehdad@gmail.com
Pr. Amina BOUCHENTOUF	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	bouchentouf_amina@yahoo.fr
Dr. Hamid EL BILALI	Univ. of Natural Resources and Life Sci. Vienna, AUSTRIA	elbilali@boku.ac.at
Dr. Bachir BENARBA	Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara, ALGERIA	bachirsb@yahoo.fr
Dr. MoezAlIslam Ezzat FARIS	College of Health Sciences, University of Sharjah, UAE	mfaris@sharjah.ac.ae
Dr. Suhad S. ABUMWEIS	Dept of Clin. Nutr. and Dietetics, Hashemite Uni. JORDAN	abumweis@mail.mcgill.ca
Dr. Mickaël RIALLAND	University of Bourgogne, Dijon, FRANCE	mickael.rialland@u-bourgogne.fr
Dr. Kaddour ZIANI	Tahar Moulay University of Saida, ALGERIA	zianivet07@gmail.com
Dr. Poorna Chandra Rao YALAGALA	Department of Medicine, University of Illinois, Chicago, USA	yalagala@uic.edu
Dr. Hicham EL BERRI	Public Health Program Manager, WHO-GENEVA	hichamelberri@gmail.com
Dr. Hala AL-OTAIBI	King Faisal University, SAUDI ARABIA	halaalotaibi5m@gmail.com
Dr. Onyinye EZEH	University of Reading, UNITED KINGDOM	onyi.ezeh@gmail.com
Dr. Andrea de la GARZA PUENTES	Fundació Sant Joan de Déu, Barcelona, SPAIN	adelagarza@ub.edu
Pr. Toufik MADANI	Ferhat Abbas University of Setif, ALGERIA	madani2000dz@yahoo.fr
Dr. Davut BALTACI	Department of Family Medicine, TURKEY	davutbaltaci@hotmail.com
Dr. Mohamed ABU-FARHA	Dasman Diabetes Institute, Kuwait City, KUWAIT	Mohamed.abufarha@dasmaninstitute.org
Dr. Farzana SALEH	University of Health Sciences Dhaka, BANGLADESH	salehfarzana42@gmail.com
Dr. Asha Murshida MUTHALIB	Univ. of Colombo, Dept. of Clinical Medicine, SRI LANKA	mujasha@yahoo.com
Dr. Halima BOUGHELLOUT	University of Constantine 1, Algeria	halima.boughellout@umc.edu.dz
Dr. Mohammed GAGAOUA	INRA - UMRH. C.R Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, FRANCE.	Mohammed.GAGAOUA@inra.fr
Dr. Farida BENMEZIANE	Chadli Bendjedi University of El-Tarf, ALGERIA	benmezianefarida@yahoo.fr
Dr. Farah NAJA	American University of Beirut, LEBANON	fn14@aub.edu.lb
Dr. Mohammed EL MZIBRI	CNESTEN. BP 1382 RP 10001 Rabat. MOROCCO	elmzibri@cnesten.org.ma
Dr. Ali Saeed AL-CHALABI	University of Mosul, Mosul, IRAQ	alisaeedchalaby@yahoo.com
Dr. Fatima Zohra LAAMIRI	Higher Inst. of Nurs. Profess and Techn. Health, MOROCCO	fatilamir1970@yahoo.fr
Dr. Nihada AHMETOVIC	University of Tuzla, Tuzla, BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA	nihada.ahmetovic@untz.ba
Dr. Juliana Gamboa SANTOS	CIDCA – CONICET, La Plata, Buenos Aires, ARGENTINA	jou_joule@hotmail.com
Dr. Linda MAJDOUB-MATHLOUTHI	ISA Chott-Mariem, Sousse, TUNISIA	yalinmaj@gmail.com
Dr. Marie Louise Berthe AHUI	Felix Houphouet-Boigny Univ., Abidjan, IVORY COAST	louise_berthe@yahoo.com
Dr. Elom Kouassivi AGLAGO	International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, FRANCE	aglagolom@gmail.com
Dr. Lamia LAHOUAR	University of Monastir, Department of Biology, TUNISIA	lahouarlamia@yahoo.fr
Dr. Lamia BENBRAHIM-TALLAA	International Agency for Research on Cancer, Lyon, FRANCE	tallaal@iarc.fr
Dr. Hajar KIAI	Institute of Food Science Research, Madrid, SPAIN	hajarkiai@gmail.com
Dr. Farid DAHMOUNE	Mohand Oulhadj University of Bouira, ALGERIA	farid.dahmoune@yahoo.fr
Dr. Omar AOUN	Djilali Bounaama University of Khemis Meliana, ALGERIA	aoun.omar@yahoo.fr

Dr. Khalid EL KARI	CNESTEN, Rabat, MOROCCO	khalidelkari73@gmail.com
Dr. Hocine REMINI	Mohand Oulhadj University of Bouira, ALGERIA	h.remini@univ-bouira.dz
Dr. Amine BELBAHI	Mohamed Boudiaf University of M'Sila, ALGERIA	belbahi.amine@yahoo.fr
Dr. Sofiane DAIRI	Abderrahmane Mira University of Bejaia, ALGERIA	sofianedairi@yahoo.fr
Dr. Makhlouf CHAALAL	Mentouri Brothers University of Constantine, ALGERIA	makhlouf.chaalal@yahoo.fr
Dr. Nabil KADRI	Mohand Oulhadj University of Bouira, ALGERIA	kadri.montp2@gmail.com
Dr. Midhat Nabil Bin Ahmad SALIMI	Universiti Malaysia Perlis, Kangar, MALAYSIA	nabil@unimap.edu.my
Dr. Akram ZRIBI	Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Sfax, TUNISIA	zribiakram@gmail.com
Dr. Amira Ghislaine DRA	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	d.ghislaine84@gmail.com
Dr. Mokhtar BENABDERRAHMANE	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	Benmok_68@yahoo.fr
Dr. Khalid BOUTOIAL	Univ. Sultan Moulay Sliman, Beni Mellal, MOROCCO	khalidboutoial@gmail.com
Dr. Samira MEZIANI	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	meziani_samira@yahoo.fr
Dr. Sanou DIA	FAO Subregional Office for Eastern Africa, ETHIOPIA	desanou@yahoo.fr
Dr. Meriem BENCHARIF	INATAA, University of Mentouri Brothers, ALGERIA	meriem.bencharif@umc.edu.dz
Dr. Ouardia OULDALI	Mustapha Stambouli University of Mascara, ALGERIA	ouuldali@yahoo.fr
Dr. Mohamed Lamine BENINE	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	benineamine@yahoo.fr
Dr. Yamina MEHDI	Univ. Center Noor Bachir El Bayadh, ALGERIA	paradis_amina27@live.fr
Dr. Mohamed ZAIRI	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	mzairi3e@yahoo.fr
Dr. Aziouz AIDOUZ	M'Hamed Bougara University, Boumerdes, ALGERIA	a.aidoud@univ-boumerdes.dz
Dr. Amina BENABBOU	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	amina_banabbou@yahoo.fr
Dr. Esmâ ZINEDDINE	Djillali Liabes University of Sidi-Bel-Abbes, ALGERIA	zineddinevet@gmail.com
Dr. Saad MEBREK	Biotechnology Research Center, Constantine, ALGERIA	saad.mebrek@gmail.com
Dr. Azdinia ZIDANE	Hassiba Benbouali University of Chlef, ALGERIA	azdinia.zidane@yahoo.fr
Dr. Fouzia TEBBANI	University of Constantine 1, ALGERIA	fouziatébani@yahoo.fr
Dr. Gulzar Ahmad NAYIK	Govt. Degree College Shopian, J&K, INDIA	gulzarbaik@gmail.com
Dr. Radhouene DOGGUI	Dept of Family Medicine, Univ. de Sherbrooke, CANADA	Radhouene.Doggui@usherbrooke.ca
Dr. Abdelhafid NANI	Ahmed Draia University of Adrar, ALGERIA	nani.abdelhafid@univ-adrar.dz
Dr. Khalef LEFSIH	Abderrahmane Mira University of Bejaia, ALGERIA	klefsih@yahoo.fr